

STUDIES IN THE DISSOLUTION OF SOAPS IN MIXED SOLVENTS.

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Alkali metal salts of long-chain fatty acids show pronounced enhanced solvency in a mixture of solvents composed of a polyhydric alcohol, a monohydric alcohol or/and a hydrocarbon or a chlorinated hydrocarbon. Solubility data in various such binary mixtures have been presented, and a discussion of their relative solvent powers has been made.

An explanation of such mix-solvency based on solvation of the different parts of the molecule through Van der Waals' forces and hydrogen bridge formation has been offered. Experimental evidences to support this theory have been presented.

The necessary conditions for a solvent or mixture to be powerful for soap dissolution has been found out to be the presence of two adjacent hydroxyl groups and a hydrocarbon dissolving portion.

It has often been observed that a mixture of two non-solvents has a strong dissolving power for a substance, whereas the individual solvents are practically non-solvents for the same. As an abbreviation of this type of enhanced solvency in a mixture of solvents of very poor individual solvent power we shall hereafter use the term 'mix-solvency' and such mixtures of complementary solvents as 'mix-solvents'.

The solutes, with which such mix-solvency occurs, generally belong to the class of compounds of high molecular weight e.g. proteins, cellulose derivatives, resins etc., the most well known example being that of nitro-cellulose dissolving in a mixture of alcohol and ether to form the familiar 'collodion'. Mardles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 2244) has listed some typical examples and Sutermeister (Sutermeister and Browne, "Casein and its Industrial Applications", 1939, 2nd Ed., p. 73) illustrates this with casein. Mellan ("Industrial Solvents", 1939) records a good many examples of mix-solvency with various resins and cellulose derivatives; Meyer (*vide* Discussions on Staudinger's paper, Faraday Society Discussion on Polymerisation and Condensation, 1935, p. 334) also mentions a case of mix-solvency with rubber in so far that the portion of rubber insoluble in benzene can be made soluble by the addition of a small quantity of butyl alcohol. A few striking cases of mix-solvency with pure resin of shellac by the author have been observed (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 300).

The theory of the process of mix-solvency is, however, little understood though various explanations have been offered from time to time based on the assumption of dissociation of the solvent (*cf.* Byron

J. Phys. Chem., 1926, 30, 1116), association of the solvent (*cf.* Barr and Bircumshaw, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 18, 99), polar and non-polar adsorption (*cf.* Esseln, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1920, 12, 801; Bogue, "Theory and Applications of Colloidal Behaviour", 1924, p. 645; Highfield, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 22, 37), solvation of varied groups (*cf.* McBain Harvey and Smith, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 239, 312; Mardles *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 1271, 2071), etc. It appears, however, that so far all studies in mix-solvency have been mostly qualitative in character and have been necessarily limited to amorphous, ill-defined or giant molecular compounds and a great advance of knowledge is expected if quantitative mix-solvency studies could be made with well defined chemical compounds of comparatively low molecular weight. Since such dissolutions are generally associated with swelling, solvation, gel-formation, etc., such a study will be of paramount importance towards a general understanding of the relationship between the lyophilic solutes and their solvents. The author's finding (Palit, *Current Sci.*, 1941, 10, 436) that alkali metal soaps show pronounced mix-solvency in suitable mixtures, has made such a study possible and the present paper records the first portion of the results obtained in this connection.

The author has observed that A-G-H mixtures (alcohol-glycol-hydrocarbon) are very powerful mix-solvents for alkali metal salts of long-chain fatty acids (sodium stearate, potassium palmitate, sodium oleate etc.), and A-G mixtures (alcohol-glycol) also exhibit this effect to a considerable extent. Quantitative data for such solubilities in mix-solvents will be presented herein and a theory of the process of mix-dissolution of soaps will be developed. Besides the evident theoretical interest, this study promises to be of great importance and usefulness in all industries which employ soap in organic solvents, and a discussion of these industrial aspects will form a separate communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodium stearate has been chosen as the representative member of soaps for study, a Merck's powdered pure variety, dried at 105-110° for four hours prior to use, being employed. The solvents are from various sources as recorded in the following list :—methyl alcohol (Merck's absolute, acetone free), ethyl alcohol (Merck's absolute), *n*-propyl alcohol (Schering-Kahlbaum), isopropyl alcohol (Alembic, India, pure), *n*-butyl alcohol (Merck, purified), isobutyl alcohol (B.D.H., Lab. reagent), isoamyl alcohol (Schering-Kahlbaum), acetone (Merck's analytical reagent), chloroform (Hopkin and Williams, Analar), ethyleneglycol (B.D.H. and Merck),

propyleneglycol (supplied by Griffin and Tatlock), diethyleneglycol (Boake Roberts & Co.), trimethyleneglycol (B.D.H. Lab. reagent), glycerol (Merck, bidistilled), α -chlorohydrin and β -chlorohydrin (B.D.H.). All the solvents in the above list appearing before ethyleneglycol, except the 'analytical reagents', were properly dried with freshly ignited Merck's pure calcium oxide and fractionated before use. The glycols were all twice distilled and the fraction boiling within two degree range in the second distillation collected. The chlorohydrins were distilled under vacuum and the products were quite neutral.

For solubility determinations, 2 g. of the stearate were taken in small stoppered conical flasks and were treated with 10 to 15 g. of the solvent mixture, delivered separately from microburettes correct to 0.02 c.c. from calculations of their densities. In experiments using glycerol, the proportions of the solvents were ascertained by actual weighing. The whole was left overnight to swell in an air thermostat (at approx. 25°) and placed next day in a thermostat (25° ± 0.2°) for minimum four hours with periodic shaking. The contents were then poured into a fritted glass crucible filter in an air thermostat at 25° and pressure applied from above through a tightly fitted rubber stopper by compressed air. The whole filtration process took 20 to 40 seconds. The filtrate was collected in a solubility bottle placed in an almost closed space, saturated with the vapour of the volatile solvent, and after weighing was analysed for sodium stearate as follows.

0.2N-Alcoholic hydrochloric acid (10-20 c.c.) was added to the soap solution and then 10 c.c. of 'analytical reagent' chloroform to prevent the formation of fine colloidal dispersion of stearic acid during subsequent dilution with water. About 250 c.c. of water were slowly added when a heavy chloroform layer separated. The clear supernatant liquid and three washings of the chloroform layer, each time with about 30 c.c. water, were collected through a rapid filter paper and the filtrate was titrated against 0.2N-KOH. The method has been tested and found to give reproducible results with known weights (0.5-1.0 g.) of pure sodium stearate to an accuracy of about 2%. Of course, when the amount of sodium stearate in solution is small, the accuracy is comparatively small, since the method employs the difference between two titrations. The values of solubility thus obtained, in the case of pure alcohols, have checked well in all cases with the values obtained by a direct evaporation to dryness of known weights of alcoholic solutions.

Since these experiments are mainly designed to demonstrate in a quasi-quantitative and not too precise manner, the profound mix-solvency

The chief feature of these curves is that all the curves show maximum, both sides of the maximum being more or less convex towards the horizontal axis, and in most cases the convexity of the right-hand side (*i.e.* nearer glycol) is more than that of the left-hand side. With the exception of methyl alcohol, all the maxima are in the region of 55 to 60% weight of ethylene glycol. These values of maximum mix-solubility (*S*) are summarised in column 2 of Table II, and the optimum compositions, *i.e.* producing maximum solubility, appear in column 3 of the same table. It is evident from Table II and curves, that this maximum value of solubility for any combination of alcohol and glycol increases with increase in molecular weight of the alcohol used. Methyl alcohol is, of course, an exception to the above general trend, which may not be regarded as quite unexpected in view of its being the first member of a homologous series.

FIG. 1.

In order to compare the efficiencies of different mix-solvents, the ordinate of the maximum point cannot suffice, since it bears no relationship with the nature of the whole curve and the solubilities in individual solvents. Hence, a new term, the mix-solvency factor is introduced. This is defined as the ratio of the total area under the curve to the area under the straight line obtained by joining the two points representing the solubilities in the pure

solvents; in other words, it is the ratio of the average solubility over the whole mix-solvency curve to the mean value of the solubilities in the individual pure solvents. The calculated values of average solubility and mix-solvency factor for these different combinations are given in columns 4 and 6 respectively of Table II.

TABLE II.

Mix-solvency factor of glycol-alcohol mixtures.

Composition of mix-solvents.	Max. solubility (S).	Opt. comp. Glycol : alcohol.	Solubility		Mix-solvency factor
			Average (s).	Mean.	
				$s_m = \frac{s_1 + s_2}{2}$	$f = \frac{s}{s_m}$
Ethylene-glycol : MeOH	4.72	40:60	3.75	2.24	1.67
„ : ethyl alcohol.	4.62	60:40	3.00	0.97	3.09
„ : n-propyl „	6.27	55:45	4.37	1.11	3.94
„ : isopropyl „	3.95	57:43	2.95	1.46	2.02
„ : n-butyl „	8.94	55:45	5.48	0.88	6.23
„ : isobutyl „	7.95	58:42	4.94	0.79	6.25
„ : isoamyl „	10.20	56:44	6.52	1.10	5.93
Diethylene-glycol : n-butyl „	4.77	52:48	3.17	0.75	4.23
Propylene-glycol : „	4.85	62:38	3.32	1.34	2.48
Trimethylene-glycol : „	1.16	50:50	0.88	0.54	1.63
Glycerol : „ „	11.42	56:44	7.11	0.35	20.3

Before discussing mix-solvency, a very peculiar fact about the solubility of sodium stearate in pure alcohols may be pointed out. The value of sodium stearate increases and decreases alternately from member to member of the homologous series of alcohols up to amyl alcohol. The alcohols with an odd number of carbon atoms show much higher values of solubility than their neighbouring alcohols with an even number of carbon atoms. Thus, in methyl, propyl and amyl alcohols, due perhaps to some steric factor, the even-numbered members are unable to solvate the soap molecule as efficiently as the odd-numbered ones. In this connection, it is relevant to point out (*cf.* Bhatnagar and Prasad, *Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 194) that the electrical conductivities of stearates, palmitates and oleates of

sodium and potassium in propyl alcohol at equivalent dilution are much higher than the values in ethyl and butyl alcohol. Fischer (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1922, 18, 1ff), however, found that with the exception of methyl alcohol, the gel-forming capacities of different alcohols for the same soap vary regularly from member to member of a homologous series. This may be taken as indicative of the fact that the factors which bring about gelation are not probably the same as those responsible for dissolution, a conclusion same as that reached by the author (forthcoming publication) from gelation studies of resins.

It should be kept in view when studying Table II that the values of maximum mix-solubility (S) and average mix-solubility (s) are much less liable to experimental error than the value of mix-solvency factor, (f), since the latter is a ratio, the denominator of which is comparatively small and subject to a large percentage error. Therefore, in comparing efficiencies between two mixtures of nearly equal mix-solvency factor, we shall consider S and s values rather than the factor, f , as indicative of their solvent power. A study of Table II leads to the following conclusions about mix-solvency. The power of producing mix-solvency effect increases with increase in molecular weight of the alcohol. For the same series of alcohol, the primary alcohol is far more powerful than the secondary one (compare data for propyl and isopropyl alcohols) and for the same primary alcohols, the straight-chained one is more powerful than the branch-chained ones (compare values of S and s for n -butyl and isobutyl alcohols). A striking and unexpected fact is that for the same glycol and different alcohols, the compositions of the solvent, which produce maximum solubility, are approximately at the same weight per cent of glycol, whereas for the same alcohol and different glycols, the maximum points do not crowd together so closely. These curves also furnish evidence against the assumption sometimes put forward without adequate experimental support that the optimum solvent composition, which is here the same as the composition producing maximum solubility, contains a definite simple molecular ratio of the two latent solvents. The optimum compositions, however, for all combinations containing glycol and alcohol (except n -butyl alcohol-diethylene-glycol) contain an excess of glycol by weight.

We have observed the variation of mix-solvency for the same glycol and different alcohols. It is of interest to study mix-solvency for the same alcohol and different glycols. In Table III are collected such solubility values, using n -butyl alcohol and four different glycols, ethylene, propylene, diethylene and trimethylene glycols and also glycerol; data on mix-solvency factor, etc. for these combinations are summarised in Table II.

Since glycerol, and probably any polyhydric alcohol resemble glycol in producing mix-solvency, the remarks made about glycols in this paper should be taken as applicable also to glycerol. In order to facilitate later discussions, the structures of the different glycols are also shown below.

TABLE III.

Solubility of sodium stearate in n-butyl alcohol-glycol at 25°.

<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol :glycol (by wt).	Solubility (g./100 g.) in mixture of <i>n</i> -butyl alcohol and				
	Ethyleneglycol.	Propyleneglycol.	Diethyleneglycol.	Trimethyleneglycol.	Glycerol.
100 : 0	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40
80 : 20	3.86	2.08	2.66	0.76	5.51
70 : 30	—	3.11	—	—	—
60 : 40	7.37	3.96	4.32	1.09	9.83
50 : 50	8.69	4.59	4.75	—	11.06
40 : 60	8.73	4.84	4.66	1.08	11.25
30 : 70	7.86	4.67	4.20	—	—
20 : 80	6.30	4.24	3.29	0.89	7.78
0 : 100	1.36	2.29	1.10	0.69	0.30

The mix-solvency curves (Fig. 2) are of the same general shape as the previous ones. In mixture with *n*-butyl alcohol, glycerol is the most powerful among this lot, considered from all aspects of mix-solvency. Of

FIG. 2.

course, it is not certain, if the same order of efficiencies will be maintained with respect to any other alcohol. Among the glycols, ethyleneglycol is the most powerful latent solvent, both with respect to the values of maximum mix-solubility (s) and the mix-solvency factor (f). Propyleneglycol comes next, followed closely by diethyleneglycol with respect to the maximum (S) and average (s) mix-solubility, whereas the order is reversed with respect to the mix-solvency factor. Trimethyleneglycol produces very little perceptible mix-solvency. This fact is noteworthy showing the striking difference in mix-solvency effect between the two isomers, trimethyleneglycol (IV) and propyleneglycol (II), the two differing only in the relative position of the hydroxyl groups. Hence, a proximity of the two hydroxyl groups is indicated to be necessary.

The role of alcohol is possibly to solubilise the remaining hydrocarbon chain of the soap molecule, for which it has rather a low solvent power, as shown by the poor solubility of stearic acid in ethyl alcohol (about 2 per 100 parts at 20°). The resulting solvency becomes high only when the hydrocarbon portion of the alcohol covers a considerable portion of the molecule. This explains the increase in molecular weight with increase of mix-solvency. It is not clear, however, why two separate alcohol molecules cannot function in the same way as a single glycol molecule. Perhaps, the two alcohol molecules cannot provide sufficient cover for the ionically bound sodium atom, while one glycol molecule effectively does.

The powerful mix-solvency of A-G-H mixture can be explained as due to the solvation of the hydrocarbon portion of the soap by a powerful solvent, say, benzene. The role of alcohol in A-G-H mixtures then becomes a minor one and consists of simply constituting a common solvent for the immiscible pair, glycol and benzene. It is now apparent why most ordinary organic solvents have very small dissolving power for soap. These solvents can hardly provide simultaneously both types of solvation necessary for the process. Table IV gives an idea of the strikingly small solubilities of soaps in common organic solvents.

The proper test of the theory developed above would be to find out a glycol and a hydrocarbon type solvent which are mutually soluble and to see if they possess power of mix-solvency for soap. A search through literature (Lawrie, "Glycerol and the Glycols", 1928, p. 375) shows that this is possible not with the simplest glycol but with its higher homologues or polyglycols, such as propyleneglycol and diethyleneglycol, which though immiscible with benzene is miscible with powerful hydrocarbon-solvents like chloroform, ethylene dichloride, etc.

An immediate appeal to experiment testified to the correctness of our theory and not only chloroform, but a host of other halogenated hydrocarbons, *e.g.* ethylene dichloride, dichloroethylene, trichloroethylene, tetrachloroethane, etc., exhibited pronounced mix-solvency in combination with these glycols. We shall term such compositions comprising of a polyhydric alcohol and a hydrocarbon or a chlorinated hydrocarbon as G-H mixtures. Thus, mix-solvency for alkali metal soap is shown by A-G, G-H or A-G-H mixture but not to any considerable extent by A-H mixtures.

The solubility data for chloroform-diethyleneglycol or propyleneglycol are given in Table V and represented graphically in Fig. 3. Since acetone has some solvency for hydrocarbons, it is expected according to our views to exhibit mix-solvency for soap in combination with ethyleneglycol. This expectation has been experimentally fulfilled (Fig. 3; Table V). The curves

TABLE IV.

Solubility of soaps in common organic solvents..

Soap.	Solvent.	Temp.	Solubility.	Observer.
Potassium stearate	Ethyl alcohol	10°	0'432 g./100g.	Chevren ^a
Sodium stearate	Do	10°	0'200	
Potassium palmitate	95% Alcohol	22°	1'430	Freundlich ^a
Sodium palmitate	<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol	50°	ca. 0'5%	Vold, Legett and McRain ^a
"	Glycerol	50°	ca. 1'0	
"	Diethyleneglycol	50°	ca. 1'5	
Lithium palmitate	Ethyl alcohol	18°	0'079/100 c.c.	Partheil and Ferie ^a
"	"	25°	0'095	
Lithium stearate	"	18°	0'041	
"	"	25°	0'053	
Lithium palmitate	Methyl alcohol	25°	0'771%	
"	Acetone	25°	0'508	Quoted by Jamieson [†]
Lithium stearate	Ether	15'8°	0'011	
"	Methyl acetate	25°	0'439	
"	Acetone	25°	0'706	
Ammonium stearate	Ether	15°	0'10	
Ammonium palmitate	Ether	13°	0'20	
"	Acetone	13°	0'20	
"	Alcohol	10°	0'70	
Potassium oleate	Alcohol	18°	1'24	Laing [‡]

^a Quoted by Lederer, "Kolloidchemie der Seife," 1932, pp. 219-222.

[†] Jamieson, "Vegetable Fats and Oils", 1932, p. 290.

[‡] Laing, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 118, 435.

strikingly show the effect of mixing a hydrocarbon with a glycol. It is further to be noticed that the maximum solubility for diethyleneglycol—chloroform occurs at about 30% weight of chloroform in the solvent, whereas for propyleneglycol-chloroform it occurs at about 42% weight of chloroform. A calculation from molecular weights shows that these two maxima neither

occur at any simple molecular ratio of the solvents, nor are at equal mol. per cent. for the two combinations (mol. per cent chloroform 27.5 and 31.5 respectively).

FIG. 3.

TABLE V.

Mix-solubility of sodium stearate in chloroform-glycol mixture at 25°.

First solvent : glycol (by wt.).	Solubility (g./100 g. solvent).		
	Chloroform —diethyleneglycol.*	Chloroform —propyleneglycol	Acetone —ethyleneglycol.
100 : 0	0.22	0.22	0.14
90 : 10	3.10	3.72	—
80 : 20	5.31	6.21	1.21
70 : 30	5.83	7.61	1.82
60 : 40	5.81	7.92	2.47
50 : 50	5.50	7.75	3.10
40 : 60	4.66	6.55	3.31
30 : 70	3.85	—	3.27
25 : 75	—	—	3.13
20 : 80	2.91	4.0.	2.93
10 : 90	—	—	2.25
0 : 100	1.10	2.29	1.36

* With reference to this combination, the first column represents ratios 'by volume' instead of 'by weight'.

An immediate corollary from the above findings is that if the same molecule can combine a glycolic portion as well as a portion having solvent power for hydrocarbons, this compound will be a good solvent for soap, and the more a proper balance between these two characters will be attained in a molecule, the stronger will this compound be in its dissolving power for soaps. As an illustration of this principle, we may compare the structures of ethyleneglycol (I) and propyleneglycol (II) and α -chlorohydrin (VI). The first two compounds have the same type of dihydroxylic structure, except that in (II) one of the hydrogen atoms of the (I) is replaced by a methyl group. As a consequence, propyleneglycol combines the two above-mentioned characteristics much better than ethyleneglycol, and hence, according to our theory, should be more powerful of the two. These deductions from theory are borne out by the fact that the solubility of sodium stearate in ethyleneglycol is 1.36%, whereas in propyleneglycol is 2.3%.

Let us now consider some derivatives of glycerol from this standpoint.

α -Monochlorohydrin.

(VI)

γ -Dichlorohydrin.

(VII)

β -Monochlorohydrin

(VIII)

α -Phenyl β -diol-propane.

(IX)

The compound (V) is glycerol, which evidently cannot be a very powerful solvent for soap due to its lack of pronounced hydrocarbon-dissolving portion, except of course, the straight hydrocarbon chain $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$. Hence, it will have some solvency for soap and will be superior to non-hydroxylic solvents, which it is (*vide* Table VI). The second compound α -monochlorohydrin (VI), obtained by replacement of one hydroxyl group of a glycol and a chlorinated hydrocarbon, which latter types are well known as good solvents for hydrocarbon and paraffin. If one more hydroxyl of glycerol is replaced by chlorine, the resulting molecule, γ -dichlorohydrin (VII) loses this characteristic feature. Hence, we should expect that the solvent power for soap will be in the order of monochlorohydrin > glycerol > dichlorohydrin. This has been experimentally found to be true as the following table shows, where the temperature of formation of isotropic solution with 10% by weight of sodium palmitate has been determined by heating in sealed tubes. The first four data are taken from a paper by Vold, Degett and McBain.

TABLE VI.

Solvent	Temp. of formation of isotropic soln. with 10% Na-palmitate.	Solvent.	Temp. of formation of isotropic soln. with 10% Na-palmitate.
Heptane	244°	Glycerol	84°
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol	137°	α -Monochlorohydrin	58°
			61° (for Na-stearate).
Diethyleneglycol	91°	$\epsilon\gamma$ -Dichlorohydrin	Above 170° (boiling point).

Some predictions may now be ventured. In comparing the two isomeric monochlorohydrins (see formulae VI and VIII) we find that the main difference between the α - and the β -compound lies in the position of the two hydroxyl groups. Since we have seen in our experiments with trimethyleneglycol that the hydroxyl group must be on the two contiguous carbon atoms to have good latent solvency for soap, we can safely infer that the β -compound will be far less powerful than the α -compound. Suppose we replace a chlorine atom of the α -chlorohydrin by a phenyl group to produce the structure (IX). This compound combines both a glycolic character and a benzoid character and hence should be a powerful solvent for soap. Attempts are being made to test the validity of these inferences and the results will appear in a later publication.

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